

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DETERMINANTS AND PRODUCTION CONSTRAINTS IN ADOPTION OF NEW VARIETY OF ACHA (*Digitaria spp*) IN PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA

Sani, M. H. and Silas, Y. G.

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology
Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, P.M.B. 0248, Bauchi, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

The study was carried out in Plateau State of Nigeria specifically in Jos South Local Government Area of the State. The major objective was to reveal the socio-economic determinants and production constraints in the adoption of new variety of acha (*Digitaria spp*) using sample of 60 farmers. The data were described and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings indicated that majority (60%) of the farmers were not in contact with extension agents; majority (65%) of the farmers preferred to adopt white Acha variety (*Digitaria exilis*) implying that it has some latent qualities such as high yielding, early maturity and high market value. The results disclosed that majority (55%) of the farmers' with age (20-35 years) and education (60%) at tertiary level influenced their adoptive behaviour. Similarly the results of the inferential statistics (regression analysis) of the socio-economic factors in the adoption rate revealed that farmers' age, education, customer's preference (market value) and high yield (early maturity) of acha variety cultivated were positive and statistically significant at $P \leq 0.05$. The R^2 value of 67.7% was disclosed meaning that the joint effects of the variable included in the model influenced adoption by 67.7%. The production constraints faced by the farmers were lack or inadequate finance, farm inputs and use of primitive methods in production as well as marketing, activities of middlemen, poor pricing and transportation. The study recommended that more awareness need to be created on the importance and production of acha nationwide by intensifying efforts to introduce other unknown high yielding varieties which might have some comparative advantages over the existing ones and more extension agents should be employed specially trained for acha production towards inventing modern technology to processing of acha.

KEYWORDS: Acha, Adoption, *Digitaria exilis*, *Digitaria iburua*, Extension and Production.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Acha is a small grain cereal crop widely grown in West Africa in the dry savannah zones and in Nigeria in the Plateau. Acha is a taxonomically difficult genus comprising about 230 species in tropical, sub-tropical and warm-temperate regions with only two main varieties (*Digitaria exilis*, and *Digitaria Iburua*) commonly cultivated in West Africa. The study was based on the premise that: farmer's preference for a particular variety of acha was because they considered it of indigenous origin and has long established tradition for cultivating, low educational and socio-economic background of farmers largely contributed to their reluctance and scepticism in adopting a new variety of acha, farmers were adequately informed about the good characteristics and economic values of the new variety of acha such that its adoption would be in large scale.

Despite the valuable importance of acha particularly the nutritive and latent properties, which is recommended for lactating women and diabetic patients, its cultivation is still very low in Nigeria. Hence, the study was consummated to ascertain the reasons for low productivity taking into consideration the following realizable objectives of the study: determine the socio-economic attributes of the farmers in adoption of new variety of acha (*Digitaria spp*) in the study area; examine the relationship between farmers' behaviour with respect to adoption; reveal farmer's preference for adopting to their traditional acha variety and ascertain the major constraints in the adoption of a new variety of acha (*Digitaria spp*) in Plateau State, Nigeria.

Scientists pointed out that acha crop received little attention from researchers and other agricultural scientists when compared with other cereal crops like maize, rice, millet, and sorghum. Hence, its adoption and cultivation are not widely spread among its farmers in Nigeria implying that the potential value of the crop is still under exploited. Acha was once considered as one of the lost crops of Africa and was completely neglected by agricultural. The crop was wrongly named as hungry rice because it is not grown to relieve hunger but because

of its quality and contribution to food security. Similarly, the term hungry rice is a misleading since it originated from the Europeans who knew nothing or little about the crop. Unknown to them, the local communities were harvesting acha not because they were hungry but because they like the taste (Harlan, 1996; Kwon-Ndung *et al.* 2001; Samson and Earl, 2007).

Ibrahim (2001) reveals that, acha (*Digitaria spp*) is a crop with a short life cycle and able to produce on poor soils. It is sometimes regarded as “grain of life” as it provides food early in the farming season, when other crops are yet to mature for harvest. Acha grains are considered to be the tastiest and nutritious of all grains. Temple and Bassa (1991) revealed that acha has about 7% crude proteins that are high in leucine (9.8%), methionine (5.6%) and valine (5.8%). Nzeribe and Nwasike (1995) added that acha has high brewing and malting potentials. Acha fits perfectly into the low, input farming systems of resource poor farmers because of its unique ability to withstand drought and tolerate poor soils. However, due to reasons such as the drudgery involved in weed control, and difficulty in dehusking the seeds; small seed size and low yields, traditional growers of the crop have shifted to the production of other crops such as maize, Irish potatoes, millets and sorghum. This is a threat to genetic resource and national food security (Vietnemeier and Borlaugh, 1996).

According to Pablo *et al.* (2003), acha (*Digitaria spp*) is cultivated and used as food and forage in the Dominican Republic Island of South America. Statistics reveals that the average world production of acha (*Digitaria exilis* and *Digitaria iburua*) together in 1999 -2003 was 257,000 tons/annum from 360,000 tons/annum, all in West Africa. The main producing countries are Guinea (128,000 tons/annum in 1999-2003, from 137,000 tons/ha); Nigeria (78,000 tons/annum from 142,000 tons/annum); Mali (21000 tons/annum from 33,000 tons/annum); Burkina Faso (13,000 tons/annum from 16,000 tons/annum) and Cote d’Ivoire (11,000 tons/annum from 22,000 tons/annum). The statistics also revealed an increase in world production from 180,000 tons/annum in the early 1960s to around 20,000 tons/annum in the early 2005, with an increase in acreage from around 280,000ha to about 360,000ha (FAO, 2001).

The production of acha is being hampered by constraints such as weed control, low yield, small seed size, pests and diseases, lack of optimum fertilizer rate, lack of improved varieties, lack of appropriate planting method to reduce the drudgery of weed control and grain processing technologies. Early to medium maturing varieties (60-120days) are found in the lower rainfall areas and can be doubled or even triple cropped in Guinea where the duration of the season permit longer duration varieties (120-150days), tend to be taller (60-75cm) and high yielding with large grain. The crop can be grown on poor, shallow, sandy or rocky soils unsuitable for other cereals, require little or no nutrient, do not prosper in saline or heavy soils and can also grow on acidic soil with very high aluminum content (Cisse, 1995; Johntson, 1985).

According to Jideani (1999), acha (*Digitaria spp*) is usually harvested by cutting with knife or sickle, tie into sheaves, dried and stored under cover. The harvested sheaves are threshed using either legs or by beating with stick it is usually processed traditionally using pestle and mortar.

In Nigeria, the value addition of acha (*Digitaria spp*) includes flour made into thick unfermented porridges, tuwo acha and fermented grains are also used for thin porridges Kunu acha, and grains are boiled with vegetables, fish or meat for eating. In some places like in northern Togo, the Lamba people brew beer tchapalo from acha (*Digitaria spp*). Acha is also prepared as *Digitaria spp* pies, *Digitaria spp* cake, and bread *Digitaria spp* chapatti, and *Digitaria spp* moimoi. It is also popped and can be mixed with other flours to make bread. Acha (*Digitaria spp*) is also associated with various religious festivities inherited from African ancestors. The grain is also considered to have medicinal properties, it is recommended for lactating women and diabetic people. The grain is also eaten cooked like rice or in stews (Subba, *et al.* 2001; Froment and Renard, 2001).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area

The study was carried out in Plateau State of Nigeria specifically in Jos South Local Government Area of the State which is the major Acha production area in the State. The Local Government consists of five districts namely, Gyel, Du, Zawan, Kuru and Vwang with the total population of 3,113,392 (157,067 male and 154,325 female) according to NPC (2006) Census figure of Nigeria. The major inhabitants of the area are Berom people and other settlers such as Ibo, Hausa, Yoruba and numerous tribes of Nigeria who are mostly traders. The area is geographically located on latitude 8°30'N and 10°10'N and longitude 8°22'E and 9°30' E.

The study area is generally known for its cold climatic condition and this is due to its location on the high altitude. The cold period is between November and February with an average daily temperature of 18°C, while it gets warmer between March and May as the rain sets in. The raining season starts in April and reaches its peak in August and ends in October. The average rainfall ranges between 1,500mm – 1,600mm per annum. The rains are mostly torrential and aerographic in nature. The soil of the area is mostly sandy loamy and silky clay loam soils. The soil colour is red-brown which indicates the dominance of iron (Fe²⁺) and aluminium (AL³⁺) ions. This is why the soil has laterite nature.

Farming has been the predominant occupation of the indigenous inhabitants of the study area. But with the discovery of mining activities, some still depend on farming as their sole occupation while others are engaged in either trading or civil service. Most of the crops grown in the area include: acha, irish potato, millet, sorghum, vegetables such as cabbage, tomato, green beans, pepper and fruit such as avocado pear.

Sampling procedure

A sample size of sixty (60) respondents was selected for the study. The respondents were randomly selected from acha farmers. The use of simple random sampling technique was to enable the respondent's equal of being selected. This simplified the procedures and eliminated bias.

Methods of data gathering

The data were gathered through primary sources which involves the administration of questionnaires, verbal interview and observation to obtain first-hand information. In the verbal interview, related questions were asked, the researcher recorded and the answers were computed to arrive at a specific conclusion.

Method of data analysis

The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (average, frequency distribution, percentages) and inferential statistics (regression analysis to arrive at a logical conclusion. This is to facilitate easy understanding of the results. The use of inferential statistics was to investigate casual relationship between variables, measure the effects of one variable on another and predict values of the dependent variable given values of the independent variable

Model specification

Regression analysis (Cobb Douglas function)

$$Y = b_0 + X_1b^1 + X_2b^2 + X_3b^3 + X_4b^4 + X_5b^5 + X_6b^6 + X_7b^7 + e_i$$

where;

- Y = Adoptive Level;
- b₀ = Constant term;
- X₁ = High yield (ton/ha);
- X₂ = Consumers preference;
- X₃ = Easy processing;
- X₄ = Colour;
- X₅ = Age;
- X₆ = Education;
- X₇ = Experience;
- e_i = error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic attributes

Table 1, discloses the age distribution of the respondents showing that majority (55%) were between 20-35 years. This indicates that more young to fairly aged people are into acha production than the older ones. Auta *et al.* (2002) agreed with this finding by remarking that age was significantly related to adoption behaviour of farmers and willingness to adopt innovation than aged farmers. Even though this finding disagreed with the common opinion that greater proportion of older farmers are more engaged in farming activities than the younger ones, it agrees with Jabil (2009) assertion that young people are more flexible to adopt farming innovation because they can easily accept risk and are less obliged to other responsibilities. Majority (63.3%) were male engaged in acha farming. This could be as a result of socio-cultural background, norms and values of the study areas. This agrees with Jabil (2009) that considering labour requirement in agricultural production,

women are less involved in the field production but however, significant in the area of processing agricultural products and marketing. The implication of this is that sex reduces the availability of labour for agricultural activities especially field production with particular reference to women. The table further revealed the educational level of the respondents indicating that majority (60%) attended tertiary institution. This means that majority of the farmers were educated to a level in which the rate of adoption of improved farm technology will not be a problem as the illiterates who were conservative and not willing to take risk. This was supported by Moku (1999) where it was observed that high level of literacy farmers positively correlated with their rate of adoption of innovation. Majority (58.33%) of the respondents had farming experience of between 11 to 20 years which indicates that acha is one of the major cereal crop grown in the study area. Haruna (2002) agrees with this findings stressing that knowledge and experiences in agricultural production has been shared among farmers since from time immemorial by passing this knowledge and experience from one generation to another. In terms of farm size it was revealed that majority (53.33%) were cultivating 0.1-1.5 hectares of land implying that most acha farmers in the study areas produce it at subsistence level with little or no marketable surplus. Also, majority (86.7%) acquired farm land through inheritance probably due to the inherent problem of land tenure system which lead to land fragmentation and its inadequacies, as well as low economic status of the farmers. This result further indicates that most acha farmers in the study area were subsistence in nature. Furthermore, majority (60.00%) declined having contact with the extension agents meaning that most of the farmers were yet to be exposed to farming practices and innovations or techniques of acha production due to lack of inadequate contact with extension services (Longo, 1990).

Production activities

Table 2 disclosed that 65% of the respondents prefer to adopt *Digitaria exilis* (white colour acha) implying that the preferred variety has some latent qualities and merit such as high yielding, early maturity, and market value. Most of the farmers (91.67%) never had exposure to any variety of acha apart from two known varieties being cultivated in the study area. This indicated that out of the 203 acha varieties discovered worldwide, only two varieties (*Digitaria exilis* and *Digitaria Iburua*) were known and cultivated in the study areas. Majority (86.6%) adopted *Digitaria exilis* because of its high yielding quality; majority (66.6%) adopted *Digitaria iburua* because of its nutrient content and majority (30%) adopted both varieties because of its high yielding. This result implies that the high yields and preference determines more income as well as food security to the farmers. The farmer's output (ton/ha) shows that majority (85%) produced between 0.1 -0.5ton/ha. This agrees with FAO (2001) reporting that Nigerian acha output was 0.5 ton/ha.

The table further revealed that majority (93.33%) and (65.00%) of the farmers processed acha by the use of mortal and pistol to pound and winnow after harvest and stored processed acha in barn, sacks or bags, respectively. The results shows the primitive means of processing and storing acha in the study area due to lack of exposure to basic modern farming facilities and techniques. This finding signifies the characteristics of subsistence farming (Iwena, 2002).

Regression analysis of adoptive behavioural factors of acha farmers

Table 3 shows the regression results. It was reveals that high yield (early maturity, high market value, easy processing, nutritional value and colour), age of the farmers, level of education and experience were significantly influencing adoption rate of various variety of acha at $P < 0.05$. The R^2 value of 67.7% was disclosed meaning that the joint effects of the variable included in the model influenced adoption by 67.7%

Analysis of economic value of acha in the study area

The importance of acha to the community was revealed in Table 4. According to Table, majority (46.67%) of the farmers gave the importance of acha in their community as sources of food, income and job opportunity implying on the overall findings that the individual farmers has peculiar importance identified with acha production as it is medicinal, traditional delicacies, used the straw and chaff for livestock.

Constraints faced by acha farmers

The constraints faced by farmers in the study area were reported in Table 5. Majority (95.00%) disclosed that inadequate capital was their major constraints, 76.67% identified land tenure system, inadequate farm inputs (50%), poor weather condition (46.67%), primitive techniques in production, processing and storage (93.33%) and inadequate access to mechanization (88.33%) implying that the scale of acha production in the study area was small scale.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

The results at hand revealed that the farmers were educated enough to try any new technology or adopt new variety in the production of acha in the study area. The choice for adoption were determined by factors of high yield, early maturity, market value, less labour intensity, good flavour and consumer's preference. The farmer's contact with extension agents was inadequate thereby making the majority to be producing at subsistence level due to the use of crude and primitive methods in production, processing, storage and marketing of acha in the study area. R^2 value of 67.7% was disclosed implying that the joint effects of the variable included in the model influenced adoption by 67.7%. The production constraints include inadequate capital and farm inputs, problem of access to mechanization and poor weather condition. The study therefore recommends nationwide awareness of acha farming in view of its medicinal and economic value, intensify efforts to introduce other unknown varieties out of the 203 varieties known worldwide to the farmers which might have some comparative advantages over the existing ones and more extension agents be recruited and trained on modernized aspects of acha farming, processing and storage.

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Table 1: Socio-economic attributes of acha (*Digitaria spp*) farmers in the study area

Predictors	Frequency	Percentage
Age (years):		
20 – 35	33	55.00
36-45	24	40.00
46-55	2	3.30
56 and above	1	1.70
Sex:		
Male	38	63.00
Female	22	37.00
Marital status:		
Single	21	35.00
Married	39	65.00
Educational level:		
Illiterate	6	10.00
Primary	6	10.00
Secondary	12	20.00
Tertiary	36	60.00
Farming experience:		
1-10	14	23.33
11-20	35	58.33
21-30	6	10.00
31-40	3	5.00
41-50	2	3.33
Farm size:		
0.1-1.5	32	53.33
1.6-2.5	16	26.67
2.6-3.5	4	6.67
3.6-4.5	6	10.00
4.6 and above	2	3.33
Land acquisition methods:		
Inheritance	52	86.7
Purchased	6	10.00
Inherited and purchased	2	3.33
Contact with extension agents:		
Yes	24	40
No	36	60

*Mean age = 34

Source: Field survey data

Table 2: Production activities of acha (*Digitaria spp*) farmers in the study Area

Predictors	Frequency	Percentage
Preferred acha variety (<i>Digitaria spp</i>):		
<i>Digitaria exilis</i> (white acha)	39	65.0
<i>Digitaria iburua</i> (black acha)	20	33.30
Both <i>Digitaria exilis</i> and <i>iburua</i>	1	1.70
Exposure to new variety:	*	
No	55	91.67
Yes	5	8.33
Reasons for adoption of <i>Digitaria exilis</i> (white acha):	*	
High yields	52	86.7
Early maturity	37	61.67
Easy processing	20	33.33
Consumers preference	58	96.67
Better taste	16	26.67
Reasons for adoption of <i>Digitaria iburua</i> (black acha):		
Less labour intensity	23	38.33
Easy germination	34	56.67
Easy to pound	35	58.33
Nutritious value	40	66.67
Traditional delicacy	13	21.67
Reasons for adoption of both varieties:		
High yield	18	30.00
Less labour intensity	14	23.33
Farm yield (ton/ha):		
0.1-0.5	51	85.0
0.6-1.0	5	8.33
1.6-2.0	2	3.33
2.6-3.0	1	1.67
3.1 and above	1	1.67
Processing methods:		
Use of mortal to pound and winnow after harvest	56	93.33
Use of threshing machine to dehull after harvest	4	6.67
Storage methods:		
Use of barn, sack or bag	39	65.00
Use of bags and drum	11	18.33
Use of bags, drum and barn	10	16.60

*Implies that multiple responses existed.

Table 3: Regression results of factors for adoption of acha varieties in the study area

Predictor	Coefficient	Standard error	t-ratio
Constant	10.566	97.985	0.110
High yield (X_1)	8.952	21.398	0.418*
Consumers preference (X_2)	14.316	13.068	1.096*
Easy processing (X_3)	-4.274	8.982	-0.476
Colour (X_4)	-93.486	70.658	-1.323
Age (X_5)	2.255	2.746	0.821*
Education (X_6)	18.011	17.428	1.033*
Experience (X_7)	-2.251	4.287	-0.525
R^2	67.7%		

Source: Field survey data. * = significance at 5%.

Table 4: Distribution of respondents according to economic value of acha in the study area

Predictor	Frequency	Percentage
Serve as food, provide income and job opportunity	28	46.67
Medicinal value for diabetic patients	19	31.67
Income and traditional delicacies	5	8.33
Chaffs and straw used as livestock feeds	8	13.33

Table 5: Distribution of respondents according to constraints

Predictor	Frequency*	Percentage
Inadequate credit	57	95.00
Land tenure problem	46	76.67
Inadequate farm inputs	30	50.00
Poor climate condition	28	46.67
Primitive technique of production, processing and storage	56	93.33
Inadequate access to mechanization	53	88.33

*Implies that multiple responses existed.

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Corresponding author

Sani, M. H.

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Faculty of Agriculture and Agricultural Technology,
Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, P.M.B. 0248, Bauchi, Nigeria

E-mail: drsanimoh@yahoo.com